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A study of the opinions of the University of Gdańsk employees on the periodic assessment of academic teachers – summary of the report

A study conducted using the method of focus groups and individual interviews by experts: Katarzyna Brachowska-Przeniosło, Magdalena Trzepiota, dr Agnieszka Popławska (C-Future consultants).

OBJECTIVES AND COURSE OF THE PROJECT

Collecting and summarizing the opinions of employees of the University of Gdańsk regarding the periodic assessment of academic teachers, as well as preparing proposals for optimization and recommendations for changes in this area.

The study was carried out in the following stages:

1. Preparation for conducting the research

- analysis of the provided survey results,
- analysis of existing tools and procedures for periodic assessment,
- analysis of the organizational structure of the University of Gdańsk,
- determination of the method for selecting representatives of disciplines for individual focus groups and refining the scope of the summary report,
- organizational meeting with representatives of the service ordering party.

2. Conducting employee opinion research using focus group method

- three meetings were held for representatives of three disciplines concerning the implemented periodic assessment of academic teachers at the University of Gdańsk,
- participants assessed the periodic evaluation from the perspective of those being assessed and those conducting the assessment (supervisors, members of assessment committees),
- each focus group meeting lasted four teaching hours,
- invitations were sent to 15–20 people per group; in total, 48 employees of the University of Gdańsk were surveyed.

3. Conducting deans' opinion research using individual interviews

- three individual interviews were conducted with deans representing three disciplines,
- the interviews concerned the implemented periodic assessment of academic teachers,
- each interview lasted 1.5 clock hours.

4. Preparation of conclusions and recommendations

- a report was prepared containing conclusions from the research and recommendations,
- the recommendations were based on the conclusions drawn from the work of focus group participants and the analysis of existing solutions carried out by periodic assessment experts (C-Future consultants).

PARTICIPANTS OF FOCUS GROUPS AND INTERVIEWS

The analysis of the regulation on the periodic assessment of academic teachers at the University of Gdańsk and the accompanying documentation made it possible to determine that the

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selection of focus group and interview participants should take into account the following categories of employees:

- employees from the teaching, research, and research and teaching groups,
- employees holding the following positions: professor, university professor, associate professor (optional), assistant professor, assistant,
- persons performing the function of team supervisors,
- representatives of assessment committees,
- gender,
- length of service.

All diagnostic meetings were conducted (3 focus groups and 3 interviews) for representatives of three disciplines: psychology, chemical sciences, and linguistics. Due to the distinct criteria for evaluating achievements in the area of scientific duties, it was decided to hold separate focus group meetings for each discipline (participants from different disciplines were not mixed).

COURSE OF WORK WITHIN THE FOCUS GROUPS AND INDIVIDUAL INTERVIEWS – GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

Participants in all activities demonstrated great commitment and motivation to contribute to the study. Some expressed enthusiasm at being asked to provide feedback on the periodic assessment, noting that, until now, they had not been consulted on this matter. Employees actively analyzed the provided documents and referred to their own knowledge and experience regarding the periodic assessment of academic teachers at the University of Gdańsk. They were also eager to share their insights on existing evaluation practices at other universities in Poland and abroad.

Participants not only identified areas for potential change but also explored ways of implementing these improvements in the context of the realities of the University of Gdańsk. The work was conducted in a friendly and constructive atmosphere. The diversity of the groups in terms of positions held, length of service, functions, and disciplines represented made it possible to gather opinions on the periodic evaluation from various perspectives.

During the sessions, some participants expressed interest in learning about the results of the earlier survey as well as the focus group and interview findings. In addition, questions were raised about the extent to which employee involvement in generating suggestions for change would translate into actual implementation. Some individuals also inquired about the timeline for potential changes.

COLLECTING EMPLOYEE OPINIONS IN SPECIFIC AREAS OF THE PERIODIC ASSESSMENT – FOCUS GROUPS AND INDIVIDUAL INTERVIEWS

Below are the collected opinions of employees from three focus group meetings conducted for three scientific disciplines (psychology, chemical sciences, and linguistics), as well as from three individual interviews with individuals holding the position of vice-deans. The results are presented in relation to the identified strengths, areas for change, and recommendations for improvements in the periodic evaluation of academic teachers at the University of Gdańsk. Additionally, we indicate differences between the views of those being evaluated and those conducting

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evaluations (supervisors and committee members), as well as potential differences between the opinions of representatives of individual disciplines. Some issues were discussed in relation to several aspects of the periodic evaluation; therefore, information about them may be repeated to some extent in various subsections.

OPINION ON THE PERIODIC EVALUATION PROCEDURE FOR ACADEMIC TEACHERS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF GDAŃSK

1. Objectives and benefits of the periodic evaluation. Meeting the needs of evaluation users. Linking the evaluation with other systems.

Strengths / Opportunities

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The evaluation is considered a valuable process – it provides an opportunity to reflect on and summarize one’s academic achievements over a four-year period (self-reflection). It offers information on whether the employee is progressing in the right direction in their development. This is information for the employee whether they are heading in the right direction in their development. Usually, the employee does not have time to analyze their achievements on a daily basis. Some noted that it is a formal requirement arising from the Act, so it is good that it is implemented. During the meetings it was highlighted that the University clearly communicates the minimum expectations for employees. It was indicated that evaluation should not be a matter of debate. It should be carried out by the University.
Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The evaluation provides an opportunity for a global view of the team – how efforts and individual and collective development paths are distributed. This is also the moment when the supervisor takes the time to individually analyze the achievements of the person. It was indicated that the current system does not lead to excessive competition. Some supervisors/committee members believe it is beneficial that the evaluation is not linked, for example, to financial matters, as this prevents internal rivalry. There were voices that avoiding too high expectations protects the interests of those who, for justified reasons, cannot meet them. There were opinions that the periodic evaluation is to control, verify work, communicate results, and motivate employees who experience difficulties in scientific, teaching, or organizational areas and the indicated goals clearly result from the available documents.

Areas for Change

Perspective	Opinions

<p>Assessed employee/ Subordinate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some employees see the evaluation as a formality to be completed every 4 years. They rarely go back to it between assessments. • It was clear during the meetings that the current assumptions of the periodic evaluation make it primarily a selective tool – used to identify those who do not meet the minimum criteria. • It was said that the system does not always identify people who neglect their duties – it is possible to avoid negative evaluations despite inadequate performance. This is a signal that lowers the efforts of other employees – it is enough to perform a “spectacular” duty once in a while. • Some employees feel that the thresholds are currently too low (an estimated 95% meet them, with only 5% failing due to serious life circumstances). • It was emphasized during the meetings that the evaluation does not serve a motivating function – it does not translate into positive consequences, e.g. financial rewards. Employees with a positive assessment may not feel motivated to maintain and develop positive behaviors. • There is a lack of differentiation (levels/points) within positive assessment. Which could provide more detailed feedback, development actions, and rewards. The current system does not highlight outstanding individuals. Opinions on this point were divided. • During the discussion, opinions were expressed that the periodic assessments do not meet employees’ needs – in particular, the need for appreciation and direction of further development is not met. • There is a lack of feedback from the supervisor, e.g. in the form of insight into the opinion of the direct supervisor and/or a conversation with the supervisor about the assessment. Employee opinions in this area were varied, among others, due to different management practices introduced by the supervisors in their teams. • In the opinion of some of the employees surveyed, the communication of the objectives, benefits of periodic assessment in management and resolution is not clear. They did not find information about the motivational or developmental goal of periodic assessment in them. They draw definitions of assessment goals primarily from supervisors and co-workers. Some differences could be noticed in defining goals within individual disciplines/teams. • Participants generally do not see a connection between evaluation and other systems, e.g., remuneration/bonuses, development).
<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some supervisors and committee members believe further differentiation within positive evaluations is unnecessary and harmful as it could divide the academic community. • Some supervisors believe that the overall criteria are too low. Expectations set in this way do not translate into the development of the university, especially in the area of science. The assessment system set up in this way protects ineffective employees, e.g. those who publish little – it is difficult to be fired. Assessment does not serve to verify the quality of work. It is an inadequately functioning mechanism where work can be evaluated. • Some noted that some employees may be highly sensitive to evaluations and feedback. Sometimes they react poorly to negative feedback. For this reason, they prefer no changes to the current system that allow avoiding difficult conversations. • An opinion was expressed that the biggest disadvantage of the assessment

	<p>system is its lack of connection with other systems (motivational, document circulation). A negative assessment is linked to the next assessment period, but a positive one does not bring any benefits. A system set up in this way motivates employees to meet the minimum. People who stand out are not appreciated (not only in terms of financial rewards, but also in terms of appreciation in general).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There has been a voice saying that employees of higher education institutions are generally in a worse situation than representatives of other industries – they are subject to too many assessments, both internal and external (including reviews, etc.).
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Recommendations for changes:

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<p>Within the focus groups, a number of ideas emerged regarding strengthening the motivational goals of the assessment and linking them with other systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An idea was put forward for a nationwide/university-wide point assessment system, where the assessment participant can compare themselves to the average results of employees of other universities/their own university. • Employees expressed their opinions regarding the motivating nature of the assessment based on a longer scale than a positive/negative assessment (alternatively, these may be collected points). At the same time, it was pointed out that differentiating the assessment would make sense if it could translate into gratification. It would also require broader justification from the assessors. • Some participants indicated that a motivating goal for them could be: increasing the university's publication potential, the achievement of which would translate into greater funding for trips, for example, to conferences. • There were opinions that in the case of a positive assessment, indicating areas for improvement is motivating to the employee. • A view was also expressed about the motivating nature of comparing one's results from subsequent assessments – this would also require providing an assessment in points or on a scale. • The issue of linking assessment with remuneration/bonuses was met with divided opinions. According to some employees, it should not be linked to financial aspects, because other systems have an impact on remuneration, e.g. related to publications. • There were voices regarding the need to link positive assessment with forms of employee recognition, e.g. a diploma. • Some participants indicated that it is worth emphasizing and strengthening the developmental purpose of periodic assessment – emphasizing in communication that the assessment is, on the one hand, evaluative in nature, but on the other hand it is a tool to support employee development. • There was a voice that different scoring applies in different systems: what is key, e.g. in the scientific area, is expected to a different extent in periodic assessment and in other systems. It is worth striving for greater consistency in the criteria in different systems.

<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was a voice that after each evaluation period, the evaluation criteria should be revised, taking into account the strategic goals of the University of Gdańsk – checking to what extent the existing criteria helped to develop the discipline and the University as a whole. If they did not support development, it is worth revising them together with the participation of the Rector's authorities. • There were opinions that if the University of Gdańsk wants to be a research unit, it must gradually raise scientific requirements. • It was indicated that the evaluation system should be linked to what the University/Faculty strategically focuses on. For example, if the level in the area of science is to be raised, this should be linked to a gradual increase in the evaluation criteria in this area. Additionally, raising expectations towards employees may be associated with the fact that a larger number of them will not meet them. It is worth establishing a staff policy in this area, e.g. is a person fired in this situation? • There was an opinion that there should be a reward (financial, symbolic, non-financial) for better results. However, this requires a point-based approach to the positive evaluation. The highest-rated individuals should be reported to the dean – they receive, for example, a diploma, funding. Decisions regarding the reward system should be made at the rector's level. At the same time, the risks of linking the evaluation with financial rewards were noticed, e.g. related to the expansion of procedures, competition. • An idea was put forward that it might be worth clearly linking the evaluation with sanctions, e.g. an employee cannot be nominated for an award if they have a negative evaluation. This currently happens because the award concerns, for example, only organizational aspects and the employee may have few publications. • It was also suggested to consider extending the evaluation scale: not only positive-negative. Although at the same time concerns were expressed that such a step raises many doubts. • An opinion appeared that it is worth introducing bonuses for supervisors for additional work – sometimes this is a lot of subordinates, and supervisors also have their own duties, e.g. scientific ones.
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Recommendations of external experts:

- **Analyzing strategic goals** in the context of their compliance with the current assumptions of periodic assessment. Determining the scope of changes that would allow for the full use of periodic assessment as a tool supporting the implementation of the strategic goals of the University of Gdańsk.
- **Clearly linking the values of the organization with the assumptions of periodic assessment**, e.g. building an organizational culture based on feedback. Communicating the connections between these areas.
- **Strengthening selected competences of assessment participants** that may affect their motivating and developmental nature, e.g. managerial competences (in the case of supervisors) or openness to feedback (in the case of employees).
- **Strengthening the role of the supervisor in the assessment process.** Introducing feedback from the supervisor in the form of a written opinion of the direct supervisor, passed on to the subordinate and the conversation.

2. Rules for awarding and communicating negative/positive assessment. Assessment participants and actions they take.

Strengths / Opportunities

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There were opinions indicating acceptance of the adopted model of awarding and communicating assessment. Some people indicated that the rules and method of awarding and communicating negative/positive assessments are clear to them. Whoever receives a positive assessment – receives clear information on a piece of paper. In the case of a negative assessment – a meeting is organized and the employee knows what to do (they have a year or two to improve).
Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There were opinions indicating acceptance of the adopted model of awarding and communicating assessment. It allows supervisors and committee members to carry out the assessment process as efficiently as possible. It was indicated that the provided assessment gives the employee a clear signal that they meet the criteria. An opinion was expressed that the assessment allows for verification of achievements (whether the employee meets the criteria and what is the reason for a possible failure to meet the requirements) and taking further steps. The assessment provides space for change – after the first negative assessment, the person is not dismissed. A voice was raised that in the case of longer absences/vacations, employees know that this time is not subject to assessment. The evaluation period is extended – the employee has more time to meet the criteria.

Areas for Change

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a lack of differentiation (levels/points) within the positive assessment. This could translate into broader feedback, development activities and rewards. Periodic assessment in this approach does not indicate outstanding people. Opinions in this area were divided. Some people did not fully agree with the currently adopted principle of awarding a negative assessment based on one negative assessment in the case of one of several main assessment criteria. There were voices that this may not be entirely fair in the case of people particularly focused on specific professional areas, e.g. scientific, which makes it difficult for them to meet the indicated requirements, e.g. organizational. There was an opinion that the employee fills in the assessment form but does not do it – there is no room for their own assessment. For some employees, the consequences of a negative assessment are not clear – it is difficult for them to find information on this subject in the available documentation. During the meetings, committee members and/or supervisors explained to employees what the consequences of a negative assessment may be. The principles adopted in this area and their communication may depend on the discipline and the team. Some

	<p>employees also referred to rumors about layoffs that occurred after a negative employee assessment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The question arose: What are the consequences of a positive assessment? The lack of clarity about the consequences can have a demotivating effect on employees. For example, it is unclear whether, after a positive assessment, the supervisor should support the employee in their further development. • There is a lack of feedback from the supervisor, e.g. in the form of insight into the opinion of the direct supervisor and/or a conversation with the supervisor about the assessment. Employee opinions in this area were diverse, among other things, due to different management practices introduced by the supervisors in their teams.
<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to some supervisors and committee members, additional differentiation within positive assessments is unnecessary and harmful, because it would lead to the disintegration of the environment. • There were opinions that supervisors write positive opinions to employees because they have known each other for years and do not want to hurt the person with whom they have a close relationship – this creates a conflict of interests in the assessment. The supervisor may also fear that a negative opinion from his side will disrupt the relations in the team and affect his "electivity" for the next term. Sometimes the supervisor's assessment influences the decision to award a positive or negative assessment too much, e.g. it prevails in awarding a positive assessment despite the fact that someone, for example, publishes little. • There were repeated voices, from supervisors and committee members, but also from subordinates, that the postulate of expanding positive feedback is impossible to implement under the current assumptions of the assessment committee's work. It is too overloaded with tasks. • There was a voice that employees do not see the consequences of a negative/positive assessment. • According to some supervisors and committee members, it is reasonable for employees to expect more extensive feedback, although this is a difficult requirement to implement. A positive assessment does not differentiate between people – a person does not receive information about what they are doing well and how well they are doing it. • The opinion was expressed that the way in which the assessment is conveyed to the employee is very formal.

Recommendations for changes:

Perspective	Opinions
<p>Assessed employee/ Subordinate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees expressed their opinions about the motivating nature of an assessment based on a longer scale than a positive/negative assessment (alternatively, it can be collected points). At the same time, it was pointed out that differentiating the assessment would make sense if it could translate into gratification. It would also require broader justification from the assessors. • Some people indicated that in the case of a positive assessment, the additional motivating nature is to indicate areas for improvement.

- A view was also expressed about the motivating nature of comparing one's results from subsequent assessments – this would also require providing an assessment in points or on a scale.
- A voice was raised that it would be valuable to work together with the supervisor to improve results in individual assessed criteria in the time between assessments. This would also require providing an assessment in points or on a scale.
- An idea was put forward to reformulate the method of awarding assessments. According to it, the employee must achieve a certain number of points in the applicable categories – and not a positive assessment in each category. In this situation, points can be compensated within individual areas. An important option to consider is whether there does not have to be some minimum level achieved in each category.
- An option was also proposed to stick to the positive/negative assessment scale, while the employee would receive an assessment from the committee in each of the main assessed criteria.
- There were voices in relation to negative assessment to introduce a clear rule that the first negative assessment is a warning for the employee and is associated with a recovery plan, and the second (after 4 years or earlier) should already have specific consequences. An opinion was also expressed that it is too long for a negatively assessed employee to have been employed for 8 years.
- A voice was expressed that the assessment should be made by external experts, which would prevent subjective assessment.
- An opinion was expressed that the employee should receive all the documentation used in the assessment process.
- Introduction of feedback from the supervisor in the form of a written opinion of the direct supervisor, passed on to the subordinate (large agreement in expressing this expectation) and/or a conversation with him/her. In the case of a conversation with a supervisor about the assessment, its importance was appreciated, although opinions were divided on whether it should be mandatory.
- A need was raised related to defining the role of the supervisor in supporting the employee's development after a negative and positive assessment. The issue of justification for the supervisor to pass on the assessment of the committee to the employee was discussed. The disadvantage of this solution was indicated that the supervisor does not participate in the work of the committee, so it is difficult for him to refer to their assessment. On the other hand, he knows his employee best and it is worth supporting him in his improvement. A voice was raised that perhaps a good basis for further work after the periodic assessment could be an assessment form filled out by the employee.

**Evaluator
(Supervisor/
Committee
Member)**

- The idea was to add an additional field to the employee assessment form, “self-assessment” – a place where the person being assessed could enter additional information that was not included in the form because it did not fit into the specific fields. This should be information that is important for the assessment, such as an explanation of failure to meet a specific criterion. The description should be concise – the space should be limited, for example, by the number of characters.
- The need to extend the assessment scale was signaled: not only positive-negative. At the same time, such a step raises many doubts.
- It was suggested that in order to increase the objectivity of the assessment, the supervisor could assess the employee in relation to more specific criteria.
- A voice was raised that due to the lack of objectivity on the part of many supervisors, it is worth considering abandoning the supervisor's opinion in its current form.
- During the talks, it was heard that the direct supervisors of the employees being assessed should be supported both in preparing the opinion and in later enforcing that the employees meet the criteria, so that they are not responsible for the opinion themselves. This causes many difficult situations. The management of institutes/departments can be included in the process.
- A proposal was made to transfer a significant part of the assessment preparation to the institutes and to hold "calibration" meetings in the management teams in the institutes – joint discussion and justification of employee assessments and then forwarding them to the assessment committees. The role of the supervisor remains to pass on the assessment to the subordinate. The supervisor is responsible for supporting the employee in their development. Calibration meetings can be a voluntary option, requested by the supervisor.
- A voice was raised that it may be worth strengthening the competences of managers in the area of objective assessment, boldly communicating it and supporting employee development, and generally working on the implementation of the university values by employees.
- An opinion was expressed that it is worth introducing feedback from the supervisor (supervisor's opinion) in the form of a conversation. The direct supervisor should see the assessment form and the criteria met by the employee, which are assessed by the Committee. The employee should learn the opinion of the supervisor – preferably at a meeting.
- The issue of the justification for the transfer of the committee's assessment itself to the employee by his or her supervisor was discussed. The disadvantage of this solution was that the supervisor does not participate in the committee's work, so it is difficult for him or her to refer to their assessment. On the other hand, he knows his employee best and it would be worth supporting him in his improvement.
- An opinion was expressed that feedback for the employee could be provided by an independent expert.
- An idea was put forward to introduce annual, mandatory monitoring meetings between the manager and the subordinate.
- Proposals were made to also assess the supervisor by subordinates or to include all employees in a 360-degree assessment. Perhaps the results should be discussed with an external expert.

Recommendations of external experts:

- Introduction of solutions that relieve the work of evaluation committees in terms of awarded ratings, e.g. preparation of an initial assessment of criteria by the employee and the supervisor.
- Implementation of solutions that make it possible to differentiate assessment and feedback, e.g. broadening the measurement scale.
- Strengthening the role of the supervisor in the assessment process. Introduction of feedback from the supervisor in the form of a written opinion of the direct supervisor, mandatory for the subordinate and during the conversation. Introduction of annual monitoring meetings with the supervisor.
- Clear communication to employees of the consequences of a positive/negative assessment for them.

3. Assessment process. Document flow. Deadlines/schedule. Appeals procedure. Communication of the assessment and training in its scope.

Strengths / Opportunities

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were repeated opinions that the assessment process, document flow, presented schedule, appeal procedure and general communication are well-developed and clear. • It was indicated that it is known where to find information on the assessment process, document flow, assessment schedule. • It was indicated that employees are provided with information on the criteria that form the basis of their assessment. • There were repeated opinions that due to the amount of work involved in the assessment, the 4-year interval is appropriate.
Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were repeated opinions that the assessment process, document flow, presented schedule, appeal procedure and general communication are well-developed. • It was indicated that the mailing with information about the assessment is sent well in advance. You even have to "click" that you have read the material. • The opinion was expressed that the possibility of appeal gives the employee the opportunity to justify their point of view and explain the difficulties.

Areas for Change

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was reported that the available documents (orders and resolutions) are prepared for the needs of the assessors. This may demotivate the assessed persons to familiarize themselves with them. The language is very formal, although legible. • It was reported that there are many documents related to the assessment and it is difficult to access all the information.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was said that although the assessment criteria were communicated to the employees, it is not certain whether it was 4 years ago – so that the employee could be assessed for a period of 4 years. • One of the employees noted that other criteria were presented to him earlier than those currently applicable to him in the periodic assessment. • In the opinion of some employees, there is a lack of mid-term assessment/verification, although in the case of some teams it is carried out by supervisors without a formal requirement.
Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was reported that a re-assessment in the appeal procedure carried out by the same assessment committee that prepared the original employee assessment may be associated with a conflict-of-interest situation. • The opinion was also expressed that it is not certain whether and to what extent employees will familiarize themselves with the information sent – despite indicating that they have familiarized themselves with the material.

Recommendations for changes:

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were opinions that in the event of the need to conduct another assessment in the appeal mode (revocation of the assessment by the rector), it would be worth appointing a second committee due to the potential conflict of interests. Alternatively, it was proposed to shorten the appeal process and for the assessment to be carried out by the appeal committee. • Suggestions were made to reduce the burden of the process in terms of the number of documents ("paperwork"). It was proposed that the document flow should be fully electronic. • It was analyzed whether, due to the specificity of experimental research, the assessment time should not be longer. Some people suggested extending it to 5 years. It was indicated that it should definitely not be shortened (less than 4 years). (CHEMICAL SCIENCES). • A suggestion was made that in the case of a negative assessment, the re-assessment should be carried out more quickly, e.g. in a year. • The idea was put forward that significant automation of the assessment process (organizing and implementing IT tools) could allow for its interval to be shortened. (PSYCHOLOGY) • There were voices that it might be worthwhile to provide training in the assumptions of the periodic assessment of newly hired employees. The training can be conducted by the supervisor. The need to refine onboarding in the organization was indicated. • A need was expressed to briefly convey the most important issues concerning the assessment from the perspective of the person being assessed. The following were suggested: newsletter, webinar, meeting. • An opinion was expressed that in the case of the assessment of vice-rectors, it might be reasonable to have the assessment carried out by external people, e.g. the Ministry. • It was pointed out that there is no information about the representatives of trade unions on the appeal committee. According to one of the participants, there should be one representative with the right to vote.

<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An opinion was expressed that in the event of the need to conduct another assessment in the appeal procedure (revocation of the assessment by the rector), it is worth establishing a second committee due to the potential conflict of interest. • An opinion was expressed that training (online, webinars) on the subject of assessment and criteria would be helpful, although the opinions of supervisors were divided on this matter. Some people believe that there is no need for this, because their teams have developed a thorough understanding of how to provide employees with information on this topic. • A voice has been raised that it is worth conducting assessment training for people who have taken on a managerial role.
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Recommendations of external experts:

- Introduction of mandatory mid-term employee-supervisor discussions on the assessment.
- Implementation of IT solutions supporting the assessment process. In particular, aimed at reducing the amount of documentation and streamlining its circulation.
- Searching for solutions to ensure impartiality in the event of a re-assessment resulting from the appeal procedure (currently carried out by the committee that issued the first assessment).
- Refinement of the method of communicating the periodic assessment – taking into account the real information needs in this respect of both the persons being assessed and the assessors

OPINION ON THE CRITERIA AND TOOLS FOR PERIODIC ASSESSMENT OF ACADEMIC TEACHERS AT THE UNIVERSITY OF GDAŃSK.

1. Assessment criteria

Strengths / Opportunities

Perspective	Opinions
<p>Assessed employee/ Subordinate</p>	<p>General comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was noted at the meetings that the University clearly communicates the minimum expectations for its employees. <p>Academic criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was reported that the criteria for academic evaluation are very clear to employees – it is clear what needs to be done to meet the required minimum. <p>Didactic criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was indicated that observations are a good source of knowledge about the employee's educational achievements. • It was reported that it is worth taking into account the opinions of students repeated in evaluation surveys. <p>Organizational criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None.

<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)</p>	<p>General comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was stated that the assessment should be based on the most objective criteria possible – currently 3 specific areas: didactic, organizational, scientific – are quite well defined, the area of their clarification is right. • It was stated that the specific areas: didactic, organizational, scientific well define the requirements for employees. They give the supervisor the opportunity to activate people who are not involved. They allow for a fair distribution of tasks to employees. Requirements and assessment in the organizational area should not be abandoned. • It was said that avoiding too high expectations protects the interests of people who, for justified reasons, are unable to meet them. <p>Scientific criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was said that it is beneficial that each discipline can define its own criteria in this area. • It was said that the criteria are achievable – for people who want to work, they are feasible (minimum). They provide space for flexible response to various situations/changes in scientific or organizational reality, e.g. when a new research topic appears and the previous one no longer has potential. When you enter something new, time is needed to achieve results. Assessment should not close the transition to a new research area. In such a situation, a person will not be productive for a year/two. (CHEMICAL SCIENCES). • There was a statement that it is good that the positions are different and research employees have higher requirements. It is good that patents are taken into account – this is fair. (CHEMICAL SCIENCES). <p>Didactic criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was reported that the didactic criteria mobilize to leave the comfort zone. In the case of a research and teaching employee, there are only two to meet – this is not an excessive expectation. Teaching employees do not conduct research, so they should develop these didactics. <p>Organizational criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was mentioned that the organizational criteria contribute to the development of employees. It is worth taking part in various activities indicated in the description of the criteria. Achieving two accomplishments in this area is considered the minimum – a liberal criterion.
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Areas for Change

Perspective	Opinions
<p>Assessed employee/ Subordinate</p>	<p>General comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was said at the meetings that the assumptions made regarding the periodic assessment make it mainly a selection tool – it is used to identify people who do not meet the minimum criteria. • In the opinion of some employees, the thresholds are currently too low (an estimated 95% meet them, and only 5% do not meet them due to very serious life circumstances). • It was said at the meetings that some of the criteria, especially in the didactic and organizational areas, have lost their relevance and that in the case of some positions/disciplines/career stages of an employee, it is difficult to meet them because the person has no influence on the possibility of achieving them.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were voices that employees undertake a number of activities that are not taken into account in the assessment process, but are important from the perspective of their work, e.g. therapeutic studies in the case of psychologists, publications related to the standardization of tools. The university does not take them into account because they are not related to its parameterization. • It was reported that in the case of some criteria, there is a lack of support from the University in co-financing activities aimed at achieving them, e.g. due to lack of funds, it is difficult to use foreign contacts in work, good publications and some foreign conferences have to be paid for yourself (LINGUISTICS) • It was stated that it is not clear how the achievements of an employee are assessed in the event of their longer absence (leave of absence, vacation). • It was pointed out that the assessment is quantitative in nature – to a small extent qualitative. • It was stated that in relation to a scientist, there is no clear criterion: constant improvement of professional competences. There is no definition of this area of requirements. • It was expressed that the criteria in general are not distributed fairly – research and teaching assistant professors are the most burdened with requirements. The employee "grabs" various activities, e.g. events, just to meet the criteria. <p>Scientific criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was said that in the case of employees coming for a post-doc, the criteria regarding publications may be difficult to meet. • There was an opinion that it is easy to fire someone for a lack of publications – there are unwritten rules. <p>Didactic criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the meetings, there was a strong voice about the low effectiveness of collecting assessment surveys of the lecturer. The preparation of the assessment by students is voluntary, which in the opinion of employees translates into very low attendance. Additionally, it was reported that the evaluation is mainly carried out by dissatisfied people. • It was reported that the assessment criteria included in the evaluation surveys are controversial, e.g. currently, a student can indicate whether the lecturer should have an observation. There was an opinion that an assessment carried out in this way may negatively affect the authority of the lecturers. • It was reported that it may be difficult for the lecturers to implement 6 achievements with the didactic criteria defined in this way. It was indicated that currently one of the possible evaluation criteria in the didactic area is supervision of awarded diploma theses – teaching staff do not conduct seminars, hence they cannot be evaluated in this area. • It was said that in the case of younger employees there is a real, objective difficulty in fulfilling some didactic criteria, e.g. supervision of awarded diploma theses. • It was said that it is not clear what publications are in the didactic area. <p>Organizational criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the meetings, it was said that this is the worst developed category. Participants indicated that aspects related to didactic and scientific criteria appear in the descriptions.
<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/</p>	<p>General comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to some supervisors, the criteria are too low in general. Expectations set in this way do not translate into the development of the university, especially in the area of science. An evaluation system set up in this way protects inefficient

<p>Committee Member)</p>	<p>employees in a special way – it is difficult to be dismissed. The evaluation does not serve to verify the quality of work. It is a mechanism that does not function properly, where work can be evaluated.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the meetings, a significant comment was made that some of the criteria, especially in the didactic and organizational areas, have lost their relevance and in the case of some positions/disciplines/career stages of an employee, it is difficult to achieve them, because the person has no influence on the possibility of meeting them. • It was reported that there are research and teaching employees who have a lot of overtime teaching – because they have such competences. It is difficult to conduct experimental research. How are they supposed to cope with the requirements? (CHEMICAL SCIENCES). <p>Scientific criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was reported that it is sometimes difficult to compare scientists to each other. Much depends on the area in which they operate – this affects the time of publication (for example, when there is no need for an experiment, time for the synthesis of compounds, then it is published quickly). On the other hand, employees can choose their own area of activity (CHEMICAL SCIENCES). • It was reported that the scientific criteria are very lenient – they do not favor the development of the University's research area. (LINGUISTICS, SOCIAL SCIENCES). <p>Didactic criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was reported that the current criteria requirements in the area: teaching achievements, are impossible to meet by a young teaching and research and teaching employee. In principle, only the sub criterion: others are possible to meet. This is very risky, for example, in the case of pursuing claims in the Labor Court. <p>Organizational criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The task was presented that from the perspective of a manager, they have a lot of organizational tasks to delegate. The system setting requirements at the level of two achievements makes it difficult to delegate these tasks – employees consider that they have done the required minimum.
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Recommendations for changes:

Perspective	Opinions
<p>Assessed employee/ Subordinate</p>	<p>General comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was a voice that different scoring applies in different systems: what is key, e.g. in the scientific area, is expected to a different extent in periodic assessment and in other systems. It is worth striving for greater consistency in the criteria in different systems. • During the meetings, a significant comment was made that it is worth thoroughly reviewing and verifying the criteria, especially in the didactic and organizational areas, in terms of their relevance, the possibility of achieving a given criterion and the possibility of influencing the person to meet the set expectations. It was postulated to generalize the description of the criteria – so that they fit different situations. • There were voices that it is worth including qualitative criteria in the assessment, e.g. social, organizational, managerial competencies. Thanks to these criteria, it would be possible to appreciate the employee's general efforts, which are not "captured" by the current assessment system. Perhaps the assessment of "soft"

	<p>aspects should be carried out by co-workers from the company. Feedback should include such criteria.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were voices that the criteria should be clearly defined/provided at the beginning of the assessment period. • Opinions were given that it would be worthwhile to divide the requirements for an employee in a percentage way, taking into account the employee's workload in individual areas – didactic, organizational, scientific. A research and teaching employee should have fewer criteria than a teaching employee. • It was reported that the defined criteria should include reviewing diploma theses, working on opinions for doctoral students, and disseminating research results. <p>Scientific criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some people indicated that the goal of increasing the university's publishing potential, the implementation of which would translate into more funds for trips, e.g. to conferences, could be motivating. <p>Didactic criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There were suggestions regarding improving the evaluation of course instructors – ensuring greater objectivity. It was proposed that this evaluation should be carried out by the Student Government. It is also worth changing the form of surveys. Additionally, it was analyzed to what extent it would be realistic and beneficial to introduce mandatory completion of surveys – opinions in this area were divided. • There was an opinion on supporting teaching staff in declaring their discipline, so that their achievements are properly assessed. A notification should be issued by the University once a year. • It was reported that it is worth including supervision of master's students, support for students who write papers/publications and go to conferences in the teaching criteria. <p>Organizational criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None.
<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)</p>	<p>General comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During the meetings, a significant comment was made that it is worth thoroughly reviewing and verifying the criteria, especially in the didactic and organizational areas, in terms of their relevance, the possibility of achieving a given criterion and the possibility of influencing the person to meet the set expectations. It was postulated to generalize the description of the criteria – so that they fit different situations. • A voice was raised that after each assessment period, the assessment criteria should be revised, taking into account the strategic goals of the University of Gdańsk – checking to what extent the existing criteria helped to develop the discipline and the University as a whole. If they did not support development, it is worth revising them together with the participation of the Rector's authorities. • It was indicated that the assessment system should be linked to what the University/Faculty strategically focuses on. For example, if the level in the area of science is to be raised, it should be linked to a gradual increase in the assessment criteria in this area. • An opinion was expressed that it may be worth including soft skills in the assessment, while noting that they may be difficult to assess. <p>Scientific criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opinions have been expressed that if the University of Gdańsk wants to be a research unit, it must gradually raise scientific requirements.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was reported that the scientific criteria for languages should be verified once again and perhaps made more stringent (the aim of the University of Gdańsk is to strive for category A.) (LINGUISTICS) <p>Didactic criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was indicated that it would be good to see the teaching load – because this is a teaching activity. Instead of a list of classes conducted by the employee, the committee should analyze the teaching load for the last 4 years. • It was reported that it is worth including supervision of master's students in the teaching criteria. <p>Organizational criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An opinion has been expressed that the employee should fulfill more than 2 organizational requirements.
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Recommendations of external experts:

- Thorough review and verification of criteria, especially in the didactic and organizational areas, in terms of their relevance, the possibility of achieving a given criterion and the possibility of influencing a person to meet the set expectations. A good course of action is to generalize the description of criteria – so that they fit different situations.
- Inviting representatives of employees from different disciplines and positions to work on the criteria – a participatory work model.
- Conducting an analysis of the burden of criteria on individual groups of employees: research, teaching, research and teaching. Striving for a fair distribution of requirements.
- Setting assessment criteria in relation to the adopted strategic goals of the University of Gdańsk.
- Inclusion of “soft” criteria in the assessment.

2. Employee evaluation form. Supervisor's opinion. Committee minutes. Positive/negative evaluation. Technical solutions supporting the process.

Strengths / Opportunities

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None
Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was reported that the employee evaluation form is legible, thanks to its tabular form. • There were voices about the positive reception of the positive and negative evaluation forms and the evaluation committee protocol. Negative evaluation protocol – provides appropriate justification.

Areas for Change

Perspective	Opinions
<p>Assessed employee/ Subordinate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a lack of differentiation (levels/points) within the positive assessment. This could translate into broader feedback, development activities and rewards. Periodic assessment in this approach does not indicate people who stand out. Opinions in this area were divided. • There was an opinion that the employee fills in the assessment form but does not do it – there is no room for their own assessment. • There is a lack of feedback from the supervisor, e.g. in the form of insight into the opinion of the direct supervisor and/or a conversation with the supervisor about the assessment. Employees' opinions in this area were varied, among other things, due to different management practices introduced by the supervisors in their teams. • It was strongly emphasized that the employee assessment form is from the previous evaluation period and its form is not modified in terms of the criteria described in the Ordinance and its annexes. For example, the criterion of continuous improvement of professional competences indicated in the Ordinance is missing. The employee also enters information that is not relevant to the currently adopted assessment criteria, e.g. if they have publications, there is no need to enter the remaining data in the area of scientific criteria. Therefore, the question arises as to which data in the form must be completed in order to receive a positive assessment. • It was quite strongly pointed out that there are no technical solutions supporting the process (or that employees do not know them). You can find some information in the repository, but this is not an assessment tool, only a parameterization tool. • There was an opinion that some data is unnecessarily entered into the assessment form metrics, e.g. date of birth, and that the employee's signature is missing. • It was reported that it may be difficult for the employee to enter classes from the last 4 years into the assessment form. • It was noticed that an error appears in the assessment committee's protocol – only scientific criteria are listed.
<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to some supervisors and committee members, additional differentiation within positive assessments is unnecessary and harmful, because it would lead to the disintegration of the community. • There were opinions that supervisors write positive opinions to employees because they have known each other for years and do not want to hurt the person with whom they have a close relationship - this creates a conflict of interests in the assessment. The supervisor may also fear that a negative opinion from him will disrupt the relations in the team and affect his "electivity" for the next term. Sometimes the supervisor's assessment influences the decision to award a positive or negative assessment too much, e.g. it prevails in awarding a positive assessment despite the fact that someone, for example, publishes little. • There were repeated voices, from supervisors and committee members, but also from subordinates, that the postulate of expanding positive feedback is impossible to implement under the current assumptions of the work of the assessment committee. It is too overloaded with tasks.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to some supervisors and committee members, it is reasonable for employees to expect broader feedback, although this is a postulate difficult to implement. A positive assessment does not differentiate between people – the person does not receive information about what they are doing well and how they are doing it. • The opinion was expressed that the way the assessment is given to the employee is very formal. • It was pointed out that the process is associated with too much "paperwork". • It was strongly emphasized that the employee assessment form is from the previous evaluation period and its form is not modified in terms of the criteria described in the Ordinance and its annexes. In the scientific area, for example, there is no space to include information about patents. The attached list of scientific achievements from the Knowledge Base does not contain the necessary information about quartiles – there are only points and IF – (there are quartiles in the assessment criteria) (CHEMICAL SCIENCES). Participants do not know where to enter/check information that is important in terms of the current assessment criteria. • It was reported that it may be difficult for the employee to enter classes from the last 4 years into the assessment form.
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Recommendations for changes:

Perspective	Opinions
Assessed employee/ Subordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees expressed their opinions about the motivating nature of an assessment based on a longer scale than a positive/negative assessment (alternatively, it can be collected points). At the same time, it was pointed out that differentiating the assessment would make sense if it could translate into gratification. It would also require broader justification from the assessors. • Some people indicated that in the case of a positive assessment, the motivating nature is the indication of areas for improvement. • A view was also expressed about the motivating nature of comparing one's results from subsequent assessments – this would require at the same time providing an assessment in points or an assessment on a scale. • An option was also proposed to stick to the assessment scale: positive/negative, while the employee would receive an assessment from the committee in each of the main assessed criteria. • A postulate was made that the employee receives all the documentation used in the assessment process. • Introduction of feedback from the supervisor in the form of a written opinion of the direct supervisor, mandatory forwarded to the subordinate (large agreement in expressing this expectation) and/or a conversation with him. In the case of a conversation with a supervisor about the assessment, its importance was appreciated, although opinions were divided on whether it should be mandatory. • There were suggestions to reduce the burden of the process in terms of the number of documents ("paperwork"). It was proposed that the document flow should be fully electronic and the necessary data should be "pulled" from the appropriate systems.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There was a fairly strong position that the employee assessment form should reflect all the criteria written in the Ordinance and its annexes. It is worth reviewing the form in terms of the validity of the criteria, e.g. whether a given type of event is still being organized. • There were suggestions to transfer some points to other criteria areas. For example, point 5 in the scientific achievements section: participation in the popularization of science should be moved to organizational achievements. • There was a suggestion that the assessment form should be adapted to the assessment criteria used in a given discipline. • It was reported that in the case of the supervisor's opinion, clear information should appear as to whether he supports the employee's self-assessment in each area. • There were opinions that currently one has to talk about one's achievements in different formats and in different versions. There should be one system that collects all the information about the employee. Data from such a solution should be automatically transferred to documents used in the assessment. Perhaps some of these functions could be taken over by an expanded Knowledge Base. It was reported that the classes conducted by the employee over the course of 4 years should be prepared by some system. • In its current form, the employee assessment form should be filled in on an ongoing basis, because completing it requires a lot of work and awareness of the criteria (which is important from their perspective). • It was reported that the employee development plan should appear in the documentation.
<p>Evaluator (Supervisor/ Committee Member)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The idea was put forward to add an additional field to the employee assessment form, “self-assessment” – a place where the person being assessed could enter additional information that was not included in the form because it did not fit into the specific fields. This should be information that is important for the assessment, such as an explanation of failure to meet a specific criterion. The description should be concise – the space should be limited, for example, by the number of characters. • A proposal was made to consider extending the assessment scale: not only positive-negative. However, at the same time, such a step raises many doubts. • It was suggested that in order to increase the objectivity of the assessment, the supervisor could assess the employee in relation to more specific criteria, indicating strengths and areas of development. • A voice was raised that due to the lack of objectivity of many supervisors, it is worth considering abandoning the supervisor's opinion in its current form or supporting it with the director's opinion. • An opinion was raised that it is worth introducing feedback from the supervisor (supervisor's opinion) in the form of a conversation. The immediate supervisor should see the assessment form and the criteria met by the employee, which are assessed by the Commission. The employee should get to know the opinion of the supervisor – preferably at a meeting. • It was quite strongly stated that the employee evaluation form should reflect all the criteria written in the Ordinance and its annexes. The requirements should be presented in the form so that the Committee does not have to look for them themselves. The descriptions of all/part of the criteria should be

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	<p>transferred to the form. Thanks to this, the Committee will be able to mark which aspects the employee meets.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• It was suggested that 3 types of employee evaluation forms should be created – for employee groups (teaching, research, research and teaching).• It was indicated that it would be good to see the size of the teaching load – because this is teaching activity. Instead of a list of classes conducted by the employee, the Committee should analyze the teaching load for the last 4 years.• It was suggested that in the case of the supervisor's opinion, some content concerning the employee should be automatically transferred so that the supervisor does not have to copy it.
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Recommendations of external experts:

- Introduction of an integrated employee evaluation sheet that collects all employee-related data in one place: applicable evaluation criteria (drop-down lists, marking of met options), self-assessment, assessment of the supervisor and the committee in terms of individual criteria. Introduction of full insight into the results of the supervisor, committee and employee.
- Update of the evaluation criteria in the applicable evaluation form in relation to the criteria described in the Ordinance and its annexes.